

THE STUDY OF IMPERFECT COMPLEXES. PART II. A MODIFICATION OF JOB'S METHOD OF CONTINUED VARIATION: STUDY OF IMPERFECT COMPLEXES BY CALORIMETRY

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The equation forming the basis of Job's method of continued variation for the determination of the composition and stability of imperfect complexes, has been modified so that the experimental procedure may be simplified and rapidly executed.

Job's method of continued variation (*Compt. rend.*, 1925, 130, 938; *Ann. chim.* 1928, x, 9, 113) has been discussed in Part I of this paper (this issue, p. 579). In that method the formula of the complex and its dissociation constant K could be found by studying a suitable property of the mixture of x c.c. of a solution of B with $(1-x)$ c.c. of a solution of A, the reaction being

From the experimental point of view, the method is, however, a laborious one as it involves the mixing of a large number of independent x and $(1-x)$ volumes of the two parent solutions for studying the property of the mixture for any one particular set of concentrations of the parent solutions.

In the present communication it has been shown that Job's method, with a little modification, is applicable also to the ordinary continuous titration experiments in which a constant amount 'a' c.c. of a solution of A is titrated with a gradually increasing amount of x c.c. of the solution of B.

Let c and pc be the molar concentrations per c.c. of the solutions of A and B respectively; let at any particular instant x c.c. of the solution of B be added to a constant volume 'a' c.c. of the solution of A and let C_1 , C_2 , C_3 be the molar concentrations of A, B and A_mB_n in the resulting mixture after attainment of equilibrium. For any volume of x , the following three relations apply

$$C_1^m \cdot C_2^n = K \cdot C_3 \quad \dots (1)$$

where K is the dissociation constant of the complex

$$(a+x)C_1 + (a+x)mC_3 = ac$$

or
$$C_1 = \frac{ac}{a+x} - mC_3 \quad \dots (2)$$

and
$$(a+x)C_2 + (a+x)nC_3 = pcx$$

or
$$C_2 = \frac{pcx}{a+x} - nC_3 \quad \dots (3)$$

Putting (2) and (3) in (1) we have,

$$\left\{ \frac{ac}{a+x} - mC_3 \right\}^m \cdot \left\{ \frac{pcx}{a+x} - nC_3 \right\}^n = KC_3 \quad \dots (4)$$

Since C_3 is a function of the only variable x , C_3 will be at a maximum when $\frac{dC_3}{dx} = 0$.

Differentiating (4) with respect to x regarding p, c, a, m, n and K as constants, and putting $\frac{dC_3}{dx} = 0$ in the resulting equation, we obtain equation (5) which is true only for that value of x , for which C_3 is maximum.

$$C_3 = \frac{pc(na - mx)}{(a+x)(p-1)mn} \quad \dots (5)$$

Putting (2), (3) and (5) in (1) we get equation (6) which also is true only for that value of x for which C_3 is maximum

$$K = \frac{c^{m+n-1} \cdot p^{n-1} (pmx - an)^{m+n}}{n^{n-1} m^{m-1} (a+x)^{m+n-1} \cdot (p-1)^{m+n-1} (na - mx)} \quad \dots (6)^*$$

Equation (6) may be written as

$$c^{m+n-1} \cdot p^{n-1} \cdot (pmx - an)^{m+n} = K \cdot n^{n-1} \cdot m^{m-1} \cdot (a+x)^{m+n-1} (p-1)^{m+n-1} \cdot (na - mx) \quad (6a)$$

when $p=1$ (i. e., for equimolecular primary solutions), right hand side of equation (6a) is zero and since c, p, m and n are finite constants, we have

$$pmx - an = 0$$

$$\text{or } m/n = a/x \quad \dots (7)$$

$$\text{since } p=1.$$

Thus, using equimolecular primary solutions of A and B, we can find out the ratio m/n i. e., the formula $A_m B_n$ of the complex using simplest integral values of m and n , provided we can find out the value of x where C_3 is maximum with equimolecular primary solutions. After determining thus the values of m and n , the dissociation constant K of the complex can be determined by equation (6) or (6b) using two non-equimolecular primary solutions provided we can determine the value of x where C_3 is maximum with these two solutions.

To determine the value of x where C_3 is maximum, we can proceed in a way analogous to that in Job's method. As in Job's method an additive molecular property P , such as molar extinction coefficient as suggested by Job or molar refractivity as used by Spacu and Popper or molecular conductivity as employed by various workers (for reference, see Part I of this paper, this issue, p 579) should be studied for the two pure

* Where $p < 1$, the value of K should be calculated by (6b) instead of (6).

$$K = \frac{c^{m+n-1} \cdot p^{n-1} \cdot (an - pmx)^{m+n}}{n^{n-1} \cdot m^{m-1} \cdot (a+x)^{m+n-1} \cdot (1-p)^{m+n-1} \cdot (mx - na)} \quad \dots (6b)$$

which can be arrived at by using $C_3 = \frac{pc(mx - na)}{(a-x)(1-p)mn}$ which is another form of equation (5).

primary solutions and for their various mixtures. Since x c.c. of a solution of B at concentration pc per c.c. is added to a constant amount 'a' c.c. of a solution of A at concentration c per c.c. at any instant, and since C_1, C_2, C_3 are the respective concentrations per c.c. of A, B, and A_mB_n in the resulting solution after attainment of equilibrium, the observed value of the property P for such a mixture is given by

$$P_{\text{obs.}} = (a+x)\{C_1P_A + C_2P_B + C_3P_{A_mB_n}\} \quad \dots (8)$$

where P_A, P_B and $P_{A_mB_n}$ are the respective molar values of the property P for A, B and A_mB_n .

Had no complex been formed, the property P for the above mixture would have been given by

$$P_{A, B} = ac. P_A + pcx. P_B. \quad \dots (9)$$

Therefore the difference Y from the additivity rule is given by

$$Y = P_{A, B} - P_{\text{obs.}} = ac. P_A + pcx. P_B - (a+x)\{C_1P_A + C_2P_B + C_3P_{A_mB_n}\} \quad \dots (10)$$

writing in equation (10), C_1 and C_2 in terms of C_3 using equations (2) and (3) we have

$$Y = (a+x) C_3 \{m.P_A + n.P_B - P_{A_mB_n}\} \quad \dots (10a)$$

$$\text{or } C_3 \{m.P_A + n.P_B - P_{A_mB_n}\} = Y/a+x = f \text{ (say)} \quad \dots (10b)$$

where f is a new function of x .

Differentiating (10b) with respect to x , we have

$$df/dx = \{m.P_A + n.P_B - P_{A_mB_n}\} \frac{dC_3}{dx} \quad \dots (11)$$

By (11), it is easily seen that when $dC_3/dx = 0$, df/dx is also zero. Thus when the concentration C_3 of the complex is at a maximum, the value of the function f (*i. e.*, $Y/a+x$) must be at a maximum or a minimum according as $mP_A + n.P_B$ is greater than or less than $P_{A_mB_n}$.

Hence, by studying $Y/a+x$ as a function of x (*i. e.*, plotting the value of $Y/a+x$ against the corresponding values of x), we can get the value of x where $Y/a+x$ is maximum or minimum, and this value of x represents the point where C_3 is maximum.

In Part I of this paper (*loc. cit.*) the molar heat content has been shown to be a property suitable for study by Job's method of continued variation. It can easily be shown that molar heat content is also a property, the variation of which can be studied in this present modified method of Job for determining the composition and the stability of a complex.

The sum of heat contents of 'a' c.c. of a solution of A at concentration c per c.c. and of x c.c. of a solution of B at concentration pc per c.c. before mixing, is given by

$$H_{\text{reagents}} = a \left\{ c.H_A + cq_A + \frac{1}{18}.H_{H_2O} \right\} + x \left\{ pc. H_B + pcq_B + \frac{1}{18}.H_{H_2O} \right\}$$

and the heat content of the mixture of the two aforesaid solutions after the attainment

of equilibrium is given by

$$H_{\text{resultant}} = (a+x) \{ C_1 H_A + c_1 q_A + C_2 H_B + c_2 q_B + C_3 H_{A_m B_n} + c_3 q_{A_m B_n} + \frac{1}{18} H_{H_2O} \}$$

where H_A , H_B , $H_{A_m B_n}$ and H_{H_2O} are the respective molar heat contents of A, B, $A_m B_n$ and H_2O , $c_1 q_A$ is the heat of solution of c mols. of A in 1 c.c. water and $p c q_B$, $c_2 q_B$, $c_3 q_{A_m B_n}$ have analogous meanings, assuming however that no change of volume of the liquid takes place on dissolution of solutes and that 1 c.c. of any solution contains 1/18 mols. of H_2O .

Hence, assuming that no change of volume takes place on mixing the solutions, the heat of reaction is given by

$$\begin{aligned} (-\Delta H) &= H_{\text{reactants}} - H_{\text{resultant}} \\ &= a \{ c H_A + c_1 q_A \} + x \{ p c H_B + p c_2 q_B \} - (a+x) \{ C_1 H_A + c_1 q_A + C_2 H_B + c_2 q_B + \\ &\quad C_3 H_{A_m B_n} + c_3 q_{A_m B_n} \} \quad \dots \quad (12) \end{aligned}$$

Proceeding as in Part I of this paper, we can prove for dilute solutions that

$$c q_A = c \cdot \bar{o} q_A \quad \dots \quad (13a)$$

$$p c q_B = p c \cdot \bar{o} q_B \quad \dots \quad (13b)$$

$$c_1 q_A = C_1 \cdot \bar{o} q_A \quad \dots \quad (13c)$$

$$c_2 q_B = C_2 \cdot \bar{o} q_B \quad \dots \quad (13d)$$

$$c_3 q_{A_m B_n} = C_3 \cdot \bar{o} q_{A_m B_n} \quad \dots \quad (13e)$$

where $\bar{o} q_A$ is the molar heat of solution of A in a large volume of water, and $\bar{o} q_B$ and $\bar{o} q_{A_m B_n}$ carry analogous significance; the three quantities $\bar{o} q_A$, $\bar{o} q_B$ and $\bar{o} q_{A_m B_n}$ can be regarded as constants.

Putting equations (13a, b, c, d, e) in equation (12) we have

$$\begin{aligned} (-\Delta H) &= a c \left\{ H_A + \bar{o} q_A \right\} + p c x \left\{ H_B + \bar{o} q_B \right\} - (a+x) \left[C_1 \left\{ H_A + \bar{o} q_A \right\} + C_2 \left\{ H_B + \bar{o} q_B \right\} + \right. \\ &\quad \left. C_3 \left\{ H_{A_m B_n} + \bar{o} q_{A_m B_n} \right\} \right] \quad \dots \quad (12a) \end{aligned}$$

The form of equation (12a) is similar to that of equation (10), and proceeding in an analogous manner as in that case, we can prove that the value of the function $(-\Delta H)/a+x$ must be maximum or minimum for that value of x for which C_3 is maximum.

The heat of reaction $\delta(-\Delta H)$ due to the successive equal additions, Δx c.c. each time, of a solution of copper sulphate at concentration $p c$ per c.c. to a constant volume 'a' c.c. of a solution of ammonia at concentration c has been determined by Siddhanta and Guha (vide Part III of this series, under publication) and the values of $(-\Delta H)/a+x$ have been plotted against the corresponding values of x [$(-\Delta H) = \Sigma \delta(-\Delta H)$ and $x = \Sigma \Delta x$].

It has been shown that for equimolecular primary solutions, $(-\Delta H)/a+x$ is maximum where $x = \frac{1}{2}a$, whence $m/n = 4:1$ *i. e.*, the composition of the complex is $[\text{Cu}(\text{NH}_3)_4]^{++}$. Using non-equimolecular primary solutions, the values of x where $(-\Delta H)/a+x$ is maximum have been utilised to calculate dissociation constant K of the complex by equation (6b), ϕ being chosen less than one. The value of K thus determined accords fairly well with that determined by Job (*loc. cit.*) and that by Siddhanta and Guha by the calorimetric application of Job's method, described in detail in Part I (*loc. cit.*) and Part III of this series (to be published).

This modification of Job's method as applied to calorimetry carries all the advantages of his method of continued variation, the study being made in an analogous manner namely by observing the heats of reaction. The modification has an additional advantage of being continuous and very rapid from the experimental point of view. It has, however, the limitation discussed in Part I of this paper that the solutions used should have negligible heats of dilution.

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